
“GREEN SLOGANS AND GRAY BEHAVIORS”: A NEW EXPRESSION BEYOND GREENWASHING IN THE CONTEXT OF ESG AND SUSTAINABILITY

"Sloganes Verdes y Comportamientos Grises": Una Nueva Expresión Más Allá Del Greenwashing En El Contexto de Esg y Sostenibilidad

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ABSTRACT

This article investigates the discrepancy between companies' sustainability communication and their actual practices, introducing the expression “Green Slogans and Gray Behaviors.” Coined by the authors, this expression goes beyond Greenwashing by capturing the complexity of corporate actions that oscillate between idealized statements and real behaviors. The research includes a qualitative theoretical review on Greenwashing, ESG, and sustainability, as well as the analysis of real company cases. The results highlight the need for a genuine commitment to sustainability, emphasizing the importance of transparency and authenticity in business practices. The critical analysis of corporate strategies from this new perspective allows for a more accurate assessment of organizations' commitment to sustainability.

Keywords: ESG, Gray Behaviors, Green Slogans, Greenwashing, Sustainability.

RESUMEN

Este artículo investiga la discrepancia entre la comunicación de sostenibilidad de las empresas y sus prácticas reales, introduciendo la expresión “Slogans Verdes y Comportamientos Grises.” Acuñada por los autores, esta expresión va más allá del Greenwashing al capturar la complejidad de las acciones corporativas que oscilan entre declaraciones idealizadas y comportamientos reales. La investigación incluye una revisión teórica cualitativa sobre Greenwashing, ESG y sostenibilidad, así como el análisis de casos reales de empresas. Los resultados destacan la necesidad de un compromiso genuino con la sostenibilidad, enfatizando la importancia de la transparencia y la autenticidad en las prácticas empresariales. El análisis crítico de las estrategias corporativas desde esta nueva perspectiva permite una evaluación más precisa del compromiso de las organizaciones con la sostenibilidad.

Palabras-clave: Comportamientos Grises, ESG, Greenwashing, Slogans Verdes, Sostenibilidad.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The growing awareness of socio-environmental issues has led companies to adopt sustainable practices and publicly communicate their commitments. However, the operational reality does not always reflect these promises. Often, the gap between what is proclaimed and what is effectively practiced is significant.

In this context, the expression “Green Slogans and Gray Behaviors” emerges. This expression transcends the simplicity of the term Greenwashing, which refers to the strategy in which companies seek to create a sustainable image, often misleadingly, to attract consumers and investors. Greenwashing is a superficial painting that masks the true environmental and social impacts of organizations.

However, reality does not easily fit into binary categories. Organizations operate on a spectrum of actions where not everything is entirely “green” or “gray.” Reality is more multifaceted, and companies frequently oscillate between idealized statements and real actions. This oscillation is the core of the emerging expression.

By recognizing this complexity through the use of the expression coined by Franco and Batista (2024a), it is understood that the pursuit of genuine sustainability requires more than well-formulated words; it demands concrete and coherent actions. The critical analysis of corporate strategies from the perspective of “Green Slogans and Gray Behaviors” allows seeing beyond appearances and evaluating the real commitment of organizations to sustainability.

This phenomenon reflects not only the need for more transparent business practices but also highlights the importance of continuous vigilance by consumers and regulatory bodies. The transition to truly sustainable corporate behavior implies a long-term commitment that goes beyond passing trends and marketing pressures. It is observed that many companies are at different stages of this journey, facing varied challenges that demand specific and adaptive solutions.

In this article, we will discuss how the expression “Green Slogans and Gray Behaviors” offers a broader view than the term Greenwashing. Real cases will be investigated, the relevance of ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) in this context will be debated, and subsidies will be presented for companies to truly commit to sustainability, going beyond mere declarations of intent.

2 METHODOLOGY

Initially, a qualitative theoretical analysis encompassing Greenwashing, ESG, and sustainability will be adopted. This review aims to better define the differences between the

dichotomies of companies' ESG approaches and their operational realities, as well as the binary nature of Greenwashing. Academic databases such as Scopus and Google Scholar will be consulted using specific inclusion criteria such as relevance to the studied topics, publication in indexed journals in the last 15 years, and keywords such as “Greenwashing,” “ESG,” and “corporate sustainability.”

To highlight the need for creating a more comprehensive expression as proposed in this article, an evaluative approach will be adopted through the analysis of case studies described in scientific articles. Cases of companies from different sectors will be presented, selected based on criteria such as the public visibility of their ESG practices and history of Greenwashing accusations. This analysis will underscore the need for a broader and more analytical approach than Greenwashing, suggesting the adoption of a wider expression. The data will be cross-referenced through thematic comparison and source triangulation to ensure the robustness of the conclusions.

2.1 Development

In the current corporate context, the incorporation of sustainable practices, corporate governance, and social responsibility (ESG) has become essential in business strategies. According to Franco and Batista (2024a), companies seeking legitimacy and public acceptance often highlight their commitments to sustainability. However, these authors point out an intriguing contradiction: the discrepancy between the promoted “Green Slogans” and the truly adopted “Gray Behaviors.”

According to Xavier and Chiconatto (2014), the concept of green marketing is broader than many people usually imagine. It is not limited to the promotion of products with environmental characteristics such as recyclable and eco-friendly but includes a wide range of activities from product and production process modifications to packaging adjustments and advertising changes.

However, these authors highlight that some companies see environmental marketing primarily as a business opportunity without necessarily translating this vision into real improvements in environmental behavior. These companies make environmental statements without evaluating the effectiveness of their products or future commitments to the environment. To mitigate these problems, various regulations have been implemented to ensure that consumers have adequate information to evaluate the environmental claims made by companies.

Franco and Batista (2024a) observe that this dichotomy between “Green Slogans” and “Gray Behaviors” challenges the authenticity of ESG approaches. While slogans can offer an attractive façade, operational practices often reveal a lack of genuine commitment to sustainability. The authors believe that the effective implementation of ESG approaches requires congruence between the

external communication of companies and their internal actions, ensuring that sustainability principles are not only rhetorical but integrated into daily operations.

In this context, it is worth mentioning the term Greenwashing, which refers to the practice of falsely promoting an organization's environmental efforts or spending more resources promoting its image as sustainable than actually implementing correct environmental practices, according to Becker-Olsen and Potucek (2013). The authors state that this concept involves the dissemination of misleading information about an organization's environmental strategies, objectives, motivations, and actions.

According to Orange and Cohen (2010), the main goal of Greenwashing is to give consumers the impression that the organization is taking responsible ecological measures when, in fact, it does very little for the environment. In recent years, Greenwashing has grown, encompassing various deceptive marketing tactics such as rebranding products as eco-friendly and promoting superficial environmental initiatives. According to the authors, labels that advertise natural, eco-friendly, recyclable, and non-toxic properties of products can be misleading and often unverified due to little oversight and vague standards.

In 2008, according to the mentioned authors, about 33% of new food products launched claimed to be “natural,” according to Dara O'Rourke from the University of California, Berkeley. Additionally, more than 98% of supposedly natural and eco-friendly products in U.S. supermarkets make potentially false or misleading claims, according to a study by TerraChoice. This study identified Greenwashing in almost all product categories, especially in children's toys, baby products, cosmetics, and cleaning products. The “natural” claim is subjective, as natural elements such as arsenic and mercury are hazardous to both human health and the environment.

According to Garcia *et al.* (2021), the case study of Vale S.A.'s Corporate Socio-Environmental Report (RCS) revealed Greenwashing practices. The research used a reflective thematic analysis, comparing the company's disclosures with information from newspapers and relevant legislation. This comparison identified significant discrepancies between what the company disclosed and the actual environmental impacts observed, especially after the disasters in the mining towns of Mariana and Brumadinho.

The study points out that even in the face of these significant environmental disasters, Vale S.A. continues to present data that can be considered manipulated or incomplete to appear more

environmentally responsible than it really is. The authors argue that the independent verification of the reports, although existing, was insufficient to prevent these Greenwashing practices.

Garcia *et al.* (2021) emphasize that Greenwashing occurs when the information disclosed in the RCS is used to improve the company's public image without a real correspondence with actions and environmental impacts. The manipulation of environmental data to appear more solidly committed to sustainability than it actually is underlines the need for greater transparency and rigor in the disclosure of non-financial information.

Another company worth mentioning is JBS. Munaier, Rocha and Portes (2022) explore how companies with a history of ethical and environmental transgressions use sustainable guidelines to try to regain consumer trust. The authors highlight that reputation and credibility are crucial elements for building the institutional image of corporations, emphasizing that consumers look for signs of environmental commitment when making purchasing decisions.

In the case of JBS, the company has been the target of criticism due to its repeated environmental and social scandals. Munaier, Rocha and Portes (2022) analyze how JBS attempts to redeem its public image through sustainable initiatives and green marketing campaigns. Despite the claims of sustainable practices, the company is often accused of Greenwashing because the disclosed information often does not correspond to its real practices. This disconnect creates distrust among consumers, making it difficult for the company to regain its image.

From the Greenwashing perspective, the authors argue that many companies, including JBS, adopt green marketing strategies aimed at improving their reputation without implementing truly sustainable practices. Munaier, Rocha and Portes (2022) emphasize that this deceptive approach can further damage the company's image when consumers perceive the discrepancy between communication and reality. They suggest that rigorous and independent verification of environmental claims made by companies is essential to prevent Greenwashing practices from compromising the integrity of the sustainable products market.

Through another lens, Franco and Batista (2024a) investigate the difference between companies' sustainability discourse and their real practices. The research highlights how many companies adopt "Green Slogans" to build a positive image of socio-environmental responsibility without these messages reflecting their practical actions. This phenomenon, indicated by the expression "Green Slogans and Gray Behaviors," shows the discrepancy between companies' environmental communication and their effective operations.

In the context of JBS, the authors examine how the company tries to promote an image of sustainability through marketing campaigns and environmental reports despite its known environmental and social scandals. Franco and Batista (2024a) explain that JBS frequently uses “Green Slogans” to project a commitment to sustainable practices, but in practice, its actions do not correspond to these promises. This contrast between discourse and operational reality leads to a loss of trust among consumers and stakeholders.

From the perspective of “Green Slogans and Gray Behaviors,” the authors emphasize that this practice involves a subtle and complex disconnection between green marketing and the company's effective actions. Franco and Batista (2024a) suggest that to combat this practice, rigorous and independent verification of companies' environmental claims is crucial, ensuring the integrity of the sustainable products market.

Furthermore, it is important to remember that the production of animal-based foods has significant and negative impacts on the environment and society. Animal-based products are associated with considerable greenhouse gas emissions, deforestation, degradation of natural ecosystems, and contamination of water and soil. Moreover, livestock is one of the main causes of biodiversity loss and soil degradation. The high consumption of water and energy in the production of meat, milk, and eggs can lead to resource shortages in various regions of the world. Thus, adopting more sustainable lifestyles and more responsible production and consumption alternatives, highlighting veganism, becomes imperative (FRANCO; BATISTA, 2024b).

Gatti, Seele and Rademacher (2019) offer a comprehensive analysis of Greenwashing research, highlighting the evolution of the topic and the growing academic attention since 2008. The review includes conceptual and empirical studies using methodologies such as case studies and experimental research, and most of the analyzed articles discuss Greenwashing in the fields of corporate communication, marketing, and management.

The authors address the issue of Greenwashing in depth, presenting criticisms of the traditional binary view that classifies corporate practices as simply true or false. They argue that this classification is limited and does not capture the complexity of the phenomenon, which often involves the selective disclosure of positive information and the concealment of negative data, potentially misleading consumers and stakeholders by creating an overly positive corporate image.

Gatti, Seele and Rademacher (2019) emphasize the need for a more elaborate approach that identifies the various types and strategies of Greenwashing. They stress that understanding these

aspects in depth is crucial for assessing the real impact of these practices on public perception and the effectiveness of CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility) policies.

Continuing along these lines, Delmas and Burbano (2011) analyze the factors that lead companies to adopt Greenwashing practices. The authors identify various motivations, including stakeholder pressure, the need to comply with environmental regulations, and the pursuit of competitive advantages. They also explore how these practices impact public perception and consumer trust.

The authors argue that Greenwashing may be a response to the complexity of stakeholder demands and the difficulty of implementing truly sustainable practices. Delmas and Burbano (2011) emphasize that while Greenwashing may offer short-term benefits, it generally results in long-term damage to the company's reputation. They suggest that greater transparency and the implementation of stricter standards can help reduce the incidence of Greenwashing.

Delmas and Burbano (2011) conclude that to mitigate the negative effects of Greenwashing, it is essential for companies to adopt a more genuine and committed approach to sustainability. This includes adopting truly eco-sustainable practices and honest communication about their environmental initiatives.

3 DISCUSSION

The expression “Green Slogans and Gray Behaviors” offers a more comprehensive and critical approach than the term Greenwashing for evaluating the authenticity of companies' ESG practices. This study seeks to demonstrate how this expression is more effective in identifying the discrepancies between companies' external communication and their internal actions, revealing a deeper and more complex analysis of corporate practices.

3.1 Vale S.A.

The analysis of Vale S.A.'s Corporate Socio-Environmental Report (RCS), mentioned earlier, revealed Greenwashing practices by comparing the company's disclosures with information from newspapers and relevant legislation. The significant discrepancies between the data presented by the company and the actual environmental impacts, especially after the disasters in Mariana (MG) and Brumadinho (MG), highlight the manipulation of information to construct a more sustainable image than it really is. The expression “Green Slogans and Gray Behaviors” captures this duality, highlighting not only the superficiality of environmental promises but also the complexity of

corporate actions. This illustrates how companies can project a green façade while in practice failing to implement significant changes in their operations.

3.2 JBS

JBS is often criticized for its environmental and social scandals and tries to promote an image of sustainability through green marketing campaigns, as previously mentioned. However, the company's real practices often do not match its claims. Studies show that despite marketing initiatives, JBS continues to face significant challenges in its operations that compromise its environmental authenticity. The expression “Green Slogans and Gray Behaviors” is particularly effective here, as it not only points out the discrepancy but also highlights the need for a more critical evaluation of corporate practices. This reveals the importance of more rigorous scrutiny and transparency in the communication of sustainable initiatives.

3.3 Broad Perspective on Greenwashing

The review by Gatti, Seele and Rademacher (2019) on Greenwashing research, discussed earlier, highlights the evolution of the topic and the growing academic attention since 2008. They argue that the binary classification of corporate practices as true or false is limited and does not capture the complexity of the phenomenon, which often involves the selective disclosure of positive information and the concealment of negative data. The expression “Green Slogans and Gray Behaviors” addresses this complexity by recognizing the nuances between communication and action, offering a more comprehensive and critical view of corporate practices.

The authors advocate for a more sophisticated approach that acknowledges the various forms and mechanisms of Greenwashing, promoting a deeper and more accurate understanding of the impact of these practices on public perceptions and the effectiveness of CSR initiatives. By adopting the expression “Green Slogans and Gray Behaviors,” it is possible to deepen the analysis of corporate actions and highlight the importance of commitment to sustainability.

3.4 Implications for Companies and Stakeholders

The critical analysis of corporate practices from the perspective of “Green Slogans and Gray Behaviors” has significant implications for both companies and stakeholders. For companies, this means that the mere adoption of green discourse is not enough; it is necessary to align internal operations with external declarations to build a truly sustainable reputation. For stakeholders,

including consumers, investors, and regulators, this expression offers a more effective tool for evaluating the authenticity of corporate practices and pressing for greater transparency and responsibility.

4 CONCLUSION

The expression “Green Slogans and Gray Behaviors” offers a critical and comprehensive approach to evaluating companies' ESG practices, overcoming the limitations of the term Greenwashing. While Greenwashing focuses only on superficial and often misleading environmental statements, the coined expression encompasses the coexistence of real “Green Slogans” with the organizations' “Gray Behaviors.” The “Gray Behaviors” vary on a wide scale of gray shades, representing nuances ranging from ethical to unethical behavior. The analysis of practical cases such as those of Vale S.A. and JBS demonstrates that many organizations build an image of socio-environmental responsibility that does not correspond to their real practices, revealing the manipulation of information to appear more sustainable than they actually are.

Adopting the expression “Green Slogans and Gray Behaviors” allows for a more rigorous and critical evaluation of corporate practices. For companies, this implies aligning internal operations with external declarations, implementing concrete and coherent actions that reflect their commitments to sustainability. For stakeholders, this expression offers a more effective tool for evaluating the sincerity of corporate practices and pressing for greater transparency and responsibility, encouraging a significant shift towards truly sustainable business practices. Therefore, it is imperative that companies align their practices with their promises and that stakeholders demand greater transparency and authenticity, thus promoting more sustainable and ethical development.

5 FUTURE STUDIES

The investigation into “Green Slogans and Gray Behaviors” opens several directions for future research. Firstly, quantitative studies can be conducted to measure the extent of these practices in different sectors, providing a more robust data base for the critical analysis of ESG practices. Additionally, research can explore consumer and investor perceptions of the authenticity of companies' sustainable practices, assessing how these perceptions impact their purchasing and investment decisions.

Another promising field is the comparative analysis between different regions and cultures, investigating how Greenwashing practices and “Gray Behaviors” vary globally and what cultural

factors influence these variations. Future studies can also develop methodologies and tools to more accurately identify and quantify “Gray Behaviors,” assisting regulators and organizations in promoting more transparent and truly sustainable business practices.

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